

Demonstration of biopolyesters and its validation for packaging applications-Draft

Deliverable 4.3

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Lead Partner: NOVAMONT

Contributor(s): ITENE

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This report represents the preliminary version of D4.3 in the framework of Subtask 4.3.4. "Production and validation of the new biopolyesters obtained".

Within the reference period, optimization studies of formulation of biopolyesters, biomaterials and films for the final applications based on results obtained in D4.2 have been carried out. In detail tests and evaluations have concerned:

- different bio-based biomaterials formulated with a new additive through reactive extrusion at pilot scale with aim to optimize materials properties, based on bio polyesters incorporating 1,4 bio-BDO into the formulation (Novamont);
- pilot scale polymerization tests with new catalyst, in order to study and verify its efficacy and stability (Novamont);
- Definition of process requirements for conversion of biomaterials into final prototypes through cast-extrusion process (ITENE);

This report represents the preliminary version of the D4.3, which will be finalised at M39 as agreed with the WP4 leader and project coordinator.

For more information, contact:

Project Coordinator: César Aliaga, caliaga@itene.com

Project Communications: James Ling, j.ling@greenovate-europe.eu

Deliverable contact: Marta Saccomanno, marta.sacomanno@novamont.com; Mariangela Aiani, mariangela.aiani@novamont.com; Felix González, felix.gonzalez@itene.com; Soraya Sánchez, soraya.sanchez@itene.com
